

coordination of the tertiary amino nitrogen² to the metal ion. Thus, in all the complexes PMU behaves as a chelating bidentate ligand. In the far-infrared region, the $\nu_{M-N} + \nu_{M-O}$ (mixed) and ν_{M-X} (X=Cl, Br) bands are observed around 300–430 and 200–300 cm^{-1} respectively. In $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the existence of bonded water has been detected based on infrared (3 570–3 510, 1 660–1 630, 850–650 cm^{-1}) and thermo-analytical data. The infrared data also reveal bidentate coordination³ of NO_3^- and ClO_4^- with Ni^{II} and SO_4^{2-} with Cu^{II} ions.

Solid state electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} -PMU complexes exhibit three bands at $\sim 10\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (\nu_1)$, $\sim 16\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F) (\nu_2)$ and $27\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (P) (\nu_3)$. The ligand field parameters⁴ like Dq (918–1 120 cm^{-1}) ν_2/ν_1 (1.59–1.67), B' (832–966) and β (0.800–0.928) have been calculated. It is clear that the low values of ν_2/ν_1 support the octahedral nature of the Ni^{II} complexes. The percentages of distortion and the ligand field stabilisation energy (LFSE) values for the Ni^{II} complexes ($\sim 34\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) agree fairly well with the values reported for Ni^{II} . Further, the room temperature μ_{eff} values for the Ni^{II} complexes⁵ lie in the range 3.2–3.5 B.M. indicating distorted octahedral stereochemistry for the Ni^{II} complexes. Also the higher magnetic moment values compared to the spin-only value of 2.8 B.M. for Ni^{II} indicate some spin-orbit coupling.

The solution as well as solid state electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} -PMU complexes exhibit two bands at $\sim 11\,900$ and $\sim 30\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The broad band around $11\,900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition, which is characteristic of a distorted octahedral stereochemistry for a Cu^{II} complex. The intense absorption around $30\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is considered to be due to charge transfer transition. The Cu^{II} complexes have magnetic moment values ranging from 1.80 to 1.92 B.M. at room temperature pointing to the distorted octahedral geometry⁶ around Cu^{II} as well as the presence of one unpaired electron on the metal ion.

The TG and DTA data obtained for PMU and a few complexes show the thermal stability order to be $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{PMU} > \text{PMU} > \text{NiBr}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU}$, and the metal oxides being the final products. Kinetic parameters like activation energy (E^* , 13.8–37.5 kJ mol^{-1}), entropy of activation ($\Delta S^* - 229$ to $-241\text{ JK}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$) and frequency factor (Z , 3.5–15.5 s^{-1}) were evaluated using the Coats-Redfern equation⁶. The low Z values and negative ΔS^* values indicate the reactions to be slow and the activated complexes to have more orderly structures than the reactants⁷.

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Synthesis and Characterisation of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene Thiosemicarbazone and 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene Semicarbazone Complexes of Nickel(II) and Palladium(II)

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WE report herein the preparation and characterisation of the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene thiosemicarbazone and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene semicarbazone.

Experimental

All the complexes and ligands were found to be insoluble in water and in most of the common organic solvents but soluble in acetone and methyl ethyl ketone. The metal ions and sulphur were analysed by reported methods¹. Electronic and ir spectra, elemental analysis and magnetic susceptibility (Gouy's method) were determined. Thermal studies were carried out in an air-oven to constant weight and the products characterised. All the reagents used were either of A.R or C.P. grade.

Preparation of ligands: 2-Hydroxy 1-naphthalidene semicarbazone was prepared by the reported method². 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene thiosemicarbazone was prepared as follows. Anhydrous sodium acetate (1.5 g) was added to powdered thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (1.0 g) in distilled

water (10 ml) with stirring. The solution was refluxed to get a clear solution. 2-Hydroxy-4-naphthaldehyde (1.0 g) dissolved in acetone was then added to it and the mixture was left in cold dark place. The resulting solid was washed several times with water, crystallised from acetone and dried in air, m.p. 274°.

Preparation of metal complexes: All the metal complexes were prepared by reacting the aqueous solution of metal ion (0.02 M) and acetone solution of ligands (0.02 M) in appropriate proportions in presence of a little dilute sulphuric acid. The reaction mixture was digested on a water-bath and the resulting solid was then washed with hot water and dried in air. All the complexes were found to be stable upto 110–20° (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
	Ni	C	H	N
Ni(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂)·H ₂ O	19.35 (19.33)	47.40 (47.41)	3.60 (3.62)	13.81 (13.82)
Ni(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ OS)·H ₂ O	18.35 (18.36)	45.01 (45.04)	3.42 (3.40)	13.10 (13.13)
Pd(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂)	30.25 (30.27)	40.96 (40.97)	3.13 (3.17)	11.92 (11.95)
Pd(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ OS)	28.91 (28.96)	39.15 (38.96)	2.96 (2.99)	11.42 (11.43)

Results and Discussion

It is known⁹ that thiosemicarbazones coordinate through S and N¹ (>C=N¹-N²H-C(=X)-N³<). The ir spectra of the complexes show the coordination through N¹ and sulphur or oxygen. The ν_{NH} ligand band remains practically unchanged in the complexes showing that N² and N³ do not take part in the coordination. The formation of M-S bond is substantiated by the decrease in ν_{C-S} from 710 (ligand) to 600 cm⁻¹ (complexes). The presence of new bands at 400–500 cm⁻¹ indicates coordination through N, O and S in the complexes.

The bands at 3 560–3 490br cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν_{OH} stretching, 730–800 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the rocking mode and 1 590–1 600 cm⁻¹ due to H-O-H bending mode, indicate the presence of coordinated water in the complexes. The square-planar structure of these complexes is indicated from their diamagnetism and electronic spectral band (13 000–14 500 cm⁻¹).

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N-2-Hydroxynaphthalylidene-o-aminophenol Complexes of some Tripositive Rare Earth Metal Ions

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THE present work describes an investigation of the complexes formed by the hydrated lanthanide(III) chlorides with N-2-hydroxynaphthalylidene-o-aminophenol (LH₂).

Experimental

The ligand (LH₂) was prepared by the recommended method¹, m.p. 186°. The hydrated lanthanide chlorides were prepared by the standard method² and then dissolved in absolute ethanol. Ethanol, DMF, nitromethane and nitrobenzene were purified by the recommended methods^{1,3}.

Lanthanone complexes were prepared as follows. A mixture of LH₂ (2 mmol), piperidine (2 mmol) and hydrated lanthanide chloride (1 mmol) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 30 min. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a vacuum dessicator over fused CaCl₂. The solid complexes decompose at 320–600° without melting. The analytical and physical data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The physical measurements were carried out as reported earlier⁴.

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